

FIELD EVALUATION OF DIFFERENT INSECTICIDE FORMULATIONS AGAINST *PHILAENUS SPUMARIUS* L. (HEMIPTERA APHROPHORIDAE) ON OLIVE TREES

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Upon the discovery of *Xylella fastidiosa* outbreaks on olive trees in Apulia (southern Italy), search for candidate vector(s) revealed that the hemipteran *Philaenus spumarius* is so far the only vector species known to be responsible for the bacterial spread in the infected area. Preliminary studies in Apulia have shown that adults of *P. spumarius* are competent vectors able to acquire and transmit the bacterium from/to olive and other known susceptible hosts, during the entire season when the adult populations occur in the olive groves. Thus, for the implementation of the containment strategies there is a need to reduce the infectious insect vector populations in the outbreak area. Since none of the current commercially available insecticides is registered for the specific control of *P. spumarius* on olives, four field trials to address the effectiveness of 13 different formulations were set up in the contaminated olive groves. Specifically, a constant number of *P. spumarius* specimens was confined, before treatment and at different period (days) post-treatment, on the branches selected on the olive trees sprayed with the different formulations. Neonicotinoids (acetamiprid and imidacloprid), pyrethroids (deltamethrin and lambda-cyhalothrin), showed rapid effects and high mortality rates; even if slower in action, similar results were obtained with etofenprox. Conversely, dimethoate (tested by using two different commercial formulations) proved to be less efficient. Whereas, buprofenzin, pymetrozine and spirotetramat proved to be not effective. With regard to the persistence, neonicotinoids, pyrethroids and etofenprox showed good persistence up to 7 days after the application. Among the organic compounds tested (kaolin, extract of citrus oil and natural pyrethrin), the strongest insect knockdown effect was obtained with the formulation based on citrus oil extracts, followed by the natural pyrethrin. However, no persistence was recorded for any of these compounds. Altogether, these results provide preliminary evidence on the efficacy of different formulations for their potential use for the biological and integrated control of *P. spumarius* toward the implementation of containment strategies for *X. fastidiosa*.